

NUDGES FOR CYBERSECURITY DECISIONS

RESUME

This briefing reports scientific evidence from a study that explores the power of nudges across different security-related decisions, to encourage safe choices when choosing a public Wi-Fi network to connect to, choosing a cloud service, smartphone encryption, and creating a strong password.

Area	Desirable behavior
Security	The desired behavior is for users to make safer choices when interacting with technology, such as choosing secure Wi-Fi networks or cloud services, encrypting their smartphones, and creating strong passwords.
Cognitive barriers	Nudges
Availability heuristic, the tendency of users to overestimate the probability of events that are readily available in memory.	Simple nudge (social norm, default, positioning heuristic), information provision, hybrid nudge (constraint, information, ordering).

information when implementing a nudge, thereby increasing the transparency of the intervention, does not necessarily decrease its effectiveness. The list of WiFi networks was sorted by security (simple nudge). In addition, the security indicators of the information condition were displayed next to the network name.

Airport Guest WiFi	secured		
Guest Airport WiFi	secured		
WiFi Airport Guest	unsecured		
Airport WiFi Guest	unsecured		
WiFi Guest Airport	unsecured		

Hybrid Nudge

PASSWORD SETTING

- Simple nudge: An additional strength bar was displayed, appealing to learned associations using color coding (green = good/secure; red = bad/insecure) and providing users with feedback related to strength, but not supporting an understanding of what a good password looks like.
- Hybrid nudge: This condition combined the simple nudge and dynamic informational text described above to support understanding that the password should be strong and how to obtain it.
- Information provision: The list of WiFi networks was ranked according to connection strength. Security indicators were displayed next to each network as information.
- The study concludes that the combination of a simple nudge and information provision, a hybrid nudge, was most effective in encouraging secure choices in the “Smartphone Encryption” and “Public WiFi Choice” decision contexts.
- The follow-up study revealed limited durability of all the impacts of the tested nudge interventions, in terms of their influence on subsequent security-related decisions in the absence of the intervention.

Airport Guest WiFi	
Guest Airport WiFi	
WiFi Airport Guest	
Airport WiFi Guest	
WiFi Guest Airport	

Simple Nudge

- Hybrid Nudge: A hybrid nudge is a combination of a simple nudge and the provision of information. This study demonstrated that the hybrid nudge was at least as effective, and in some decision contexts even more effective, in encouraging safe choices than the simple nudge alone. This suggests that including

INFORMATIVE BOX

For whom

Smartphone users. The study was conducted with participants living in the United States and aged 18 or older.

Where

The study was conducted on the online platform Mechanical Turk, an artificial testing environment with scenarios that simulate real interaction.

How

Nudges were delivered to users' phones through interventions designed in the study.

Nudge category

Digital nudge

REFERENCE

Zimmermann and Renaud. 2021. *The Nudge Puzzle: Matching Nudge Interventions to Cybersecurity Decisions*. ACM Trans. Comput.-Hum. Interact.